

Advanced protein-embedded bimetallic nanocomposite optimized for *in vivo* fluorescence and magnetic resonance bimodal imaging

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ABSTRACT

Hypothesis: The development of bimodal imaging probes represents a hot topic of current research. Herein, we deal with developing an innovative bimodal contrast agent enabling fluorescence imaging (FI)/magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and, simultaneously, consisting of biocompatible nanostructures. Optimized synthesis of advanced protein-embedded bimetallic (APEBM) nanocomposite containing luminescent gold nanoclusters (AuNC) and superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPION), suitable for *in vivo* dual-modal FI/MR imaging is reported.

Experiments: The APEBM nanocomposite was prepared by a specific sequential one-pot green synthetic approach that is optimized to increase metals (Au, Fe) content and, consequently, the imaging ability of the resulting nanostructures. The protein matrix, represented by serum albumin, was intentionally chosen, and used since it creates an efficient protein corona for both types of optically/magnetically-susceptible nanostructures (AuNC, SPION) and ensures biocompatibility of the resulting APEBM nanocomposite although it contains elevated metal concentrations (approx. 1 mg·mL⁻¹ of Au, around 0.3 mg·mL⁻¹ of Fe). *In vitro* and *in vivo* imaging was performed.

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Findings: Successful *in vivo* FI and MRI recorded in healthy mice corroborated the applicability of the APEBM nanocomposite and, simultaneously, served as a proof of concept concerning the potential future exploitation of this new FI/MRI bimodal contrast agent in preclinical and clinical practice.

1. Introduction

Bimodal and/or multimodal contrast agents are frequently asked in preclinical and clinical practice [1] since they can lead to improved localization and sensitivity of a chosen target while using a single injection, mitigating the effects of invasive monitoring. Bimodal imaging probes composed of fluorescent (especially that emitting in the near-infrared region, NIR) and magnetically susceptible parts fulfil both requirements at once, i.e., high sensitivity and unlimited spatial resolution, respectively, overcoming thus the limitations associated with the stand-alone systems [2,3]. Moreover, owing to the unique conjunction of two physical phenomena, luminescence and superparamagnetism, within one contrast agent (i.e., one probe for dual-modal monitoring), *in vivo* imaging is going to become less time-consuming and cost-effective, meeting thus current social and economic requirements. Over the past two years, there have been published more than one hundred scientific reviews (according to Web of Science) dealing with multimodal and *in vivo* imaging. Similarly, the topic of multimodal *in vivo* imaging exploiting nanoarchitectures, nanostructures, and/or nanocomposites of different kinds and compositions is very popular among scientists; almost three hundred papers have been published in recent two years (based on literature investigation using Web of Science). Thus, this research field is undoubtedly fancy and quickly developing.

Nanocomposites are frequently designed in core-shell and/or core-shell-shell architectures, comprising an inorganic core with organic layer/s around [4,5]. Another strategy embodies entrapping functional components into some matrices/scaffolds, such as metal-organic frameworks [6,7], various graphene oxides [8,9], mesoporous silica [10], silica/organosilica cross-linked block copolymer micelles [11,12], and/or proteins [13,14]. Inspired by our latest research [15] as well as by other researchers, serum albumin was chosen as a protein matrix/template for the incorporation of luminescent gold nanoclusters (AuNC) and superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPION) in the present work. Serum albumin, a well-known efficient transportation protein found in vertebrate blood, helps achieve better biocompatibility and prolongs the blood circulation lifetime of functional nanostructures (e.g., [16–19]). The step of biomimetic coating, ensuring biocompatibility of functional nanostructures in living organisms (e.g., [7,20–23]), can be thus avoided, consequently, the synthesis becomes simpler and faster.

Nanocomposites consisting of albumin conjugated with nanostructures composed of gold and gadolinium for *in vivo* FI/MR imaging were prepared and published [24,25]. Both of these bimetallic nanocomposites [24,25] possess magneto-luminescent properties; however, they are based on gadolinium ions that are generally considered toxic and represent potential risks to the environment and human health [26]. Therefore, one should rather avoid the usage of Gd(III) ions and concentrate on benign iron ions instead [27–29]. Beneficial for iron oxide usage in bimetallic nanocomposites intended to be exploited in *in vivo* FI/MR imaging is also a significant number of clinically approved imaging iron-oxide-bearing nanoparticles [30].

Herein, we developed the APEBM (advanced protein-embedded bimetallic) nanocomposite, which was tested as FI/MRI contrast agent *in vivo*. The APEBM nanocomposite is inspired by our previous work [15]; however, there are substantial changes in the preparation procedure developed and described by us in the current work. In fact, we wanted to develop a versatile and robust green synthesis of bimodal (and potentially multimodal) contrast agents, meaning that any other desired metal and/or functionality can be easily added/introduced while the stability of the final functional nanocomposite is maintained and, simultaneously, its applicability improved. To the best of our knowledge,

another system containing luminescent AuNC-SPION and simultaneously demonstrating *in vivo* bimodal imaging capability has not been published yet.

Prior to the subcutaneous injection (aimed to assess the suitability of the nanocomposite for optical imaging, similarly as in [31] into healthy mice and FI/MRI measurements, the APEBM nanocomposite was characterized by appropriate experimental techniques including UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy, steady-state fluorescence, high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), dynamic light scattering (DLS), zeta potential measurements, MR imaging, and relaxometry. Healthy cell (RPE-1) viability in the presence of the APEBM nanocomposite was assessed employing calcein assay. The results of cytotoxicity corroborated the expected biocompatibility that is most probably inherited from the components of the APEBM nanocomposite. Tests of fluorescence signal stability of APEBM nanocomposites in different media (e.g., PBS and cultivation medium) at various temperatures were investigated and revealed relatively stable integrated fluorescence emission that was superior to the average integrated fluorescence emission intensity obtained in deionized water. Moreover, fluorescence emission intensity of APEBM nanocomposites in the presence of HeLa cancer cells was checked after 1, 2, and 24 h of cells incubation (within the cultivation medium). The results confirmed fluorescence signal stability even in the presence of HeLa cells.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Used chemicals

2.1.1. Chemicals for the APEBM nanocomposite synthesis

Bovine serum albumin (BSA; greater than 98%), gold(III) chloride trihydrate ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\geq 99.9\%$), iron(III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\geq 99\%$), and sodium hydroxide (NaOH; $\geq 98.0\%$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Saint Louis, MO, USA) and used as received (without any further purification) for all experiments. Deionized water was prepared by purging Milli-Q purified water (Millipore Corporation, Bedford, MA, USA) and used for fluorescence spectroscopy and DLS measurements.

2.1.2. Chemicals for ICP-MS

Nitric acid (69%, Analpure) and hydrochloric acid (36%, Analpure) certified reference materials of calibration standard solution ASTASOL® of Au, Fe ($1.000 \pm 2 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) and INT-MIX 1 ($10.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) were purchased from Analytika, Ltd., Czech Republic. Ultrapure 18.2 M Ω cm water was prepared using a Milli-Q reference water purification system (Millipore Corp. Molsheim, France) and used only for ICP-MS analyses.

2.1.3. Chemicals for Calcein-AM assay and fluorescence signal stability experiments

Fetal bovine serum (FBS), L-glutamine, Penicillin-Streptomycin, and trypsin (from the porcine pancreas) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Saint Louis, MO, USA). Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, 11054) and Calcein-AM salt were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). Sodium chloride (NaCl; p.a.), potassium chloride (KCl; p.a.), potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4 ; p.a.), and disodium hydrogen phosphate (Na_2HPO_4 ; p.a.) were purchased from Penta chemicals (Prague, Czech Republic). Healthy RPE-1 cell line was obtained from M. Mistrík (Institute of Molecular and Translational Medicine, Olomouc, Czech Republic).

2.1.4. Chemicals for *in vivo* imaging experiments

Isoflurane (5% for induction and 1.5–2% for maintenance) was purchased from Baxter (Deerfield, IL, USA), and an eye cream Ophthalmo-Septonex was purchased from Zentiva (Prague, Czech Republic).

2.2. Synthesis of the APEBM nanocomposite, purification, concentrate formation, and storage conditions

The synthetic procedure of the APEBM nanocomposite system is an optimized, specifically modified version of the one-pot synthesis we applied in our previous work devoted to the preparation of bimetallic nanocomposites by green chemical approach [15]. Briefly, $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (200 μL , 0.1 M) was introduced into a microcentrifuge tube. Subsequently, BSA solution (500 μL , 66.43 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) was slowly added while constantly mixed with a pipette (see video in SI). Instantly after that, the same amount of BSA (500 μL , 66.43 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) was analogously pipetted, and the reaction mixture was then swirled in a vortex at 3000 rpm (kept for all further steps when the same vortex was used). Importantly, visible agglomerates were formed during both steps of protein solution addition but gradually dissolved due to the constant mixing with a pipette. NaOH (57.5 μL , 1 M) was rapidly introduced and placed into the tube five minutes later. Then, the tube content was immediately swirled in the vortex. The reaction solution became cloudy, but after several minutes, it started to clear up. Ten minutes later, HAuCl_4 (800 μL , 25 mM) was slowly added while constantly mixed. The gradual formation of a cloudy solution was observed again. The tube content was swirled in the vortex, and five minutes later, NaOH (142.5 μL , 1 M) was quickly introduced into the solution. Then, the tube was swirled in the vortex for the last time, immediately accompanied by the solution clearing up. Subsequently, the microcentrifuge tube was put into a dry bath incubator for 22.5 h, where the temperature was set to 50 °C. The as-prepared sample is of orange-brown colour without any aggregate or agglomerate visible to the naked eye. It must be noted that before putting the tube into the dry bath incubator, the solution could sometimes appear mildly cloudy, but this should eventually disappear after several tens of minutes during the incubation at around 50 °C.

After maturing inside a dry bath incubator, the sample was dialyzed with a 14 kDa cut-off dialysis membrane (regenerated cellulose, Membra-Cel™) against deionized water. Dialysis was performed at room temperature (22 °C) for 5 h, with deionized water being changed four times: after 30 min, 45 min, 60 min, and 75 min. For the cell viability experiments, a concentrated form of the sample was prepared using a centrifugal concentrator (30 kDa). The rotational centrifugal force (RCF) was set to 3000 g, and the centrifugation lasted for 5 min. This process was done repeatedly until the chosen concentration was reached. Dialyzed and concentrated samples were then stored in the dark at 4 °C.

2.3. Characterization techniques

2.3.1. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analysis

A representative APEBM sample was drop-casted (2–4 μL) on glow discharged TEM copper grid covered with holey carbon and allowed to dry spontaneously at room temperature. Then, the sample was measured by HR-TEM Titan G2 60–300 (FEI, Hillsboro, OR, USA) with an image corrector with an accelerating voltage of 300 kV. Images were taken with a BM UltraScan CCD camera (Gatan, Pleasanton, CA, USA). Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (EDS) was performed in STEM mode by a Super-X system with four silicon drift detectors (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA). STEM images were taken with an HAADF detector 3000 (Fishione, Export, PA, USA). HAADF mode of STEM is intentionally used to better visualize NCs because heavier elements appear bright, while lighter elements appear dark.

2.3.2. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)

The total Au and Fe concentrations were determined by a validated ICP-MS method employing a microwave-assisted digestion of the APEBM nanocomposite matrix [14]. Briefly, each sample was completely dried using a vacuum rotary evaporator Concentrator plus (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany) prior to the ICP-MS analysis. The dried samples were digested using a mixture of 2 mL of concentrated nitric acid and 2 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid in the MLS 1200 mega closed vessel microwave digestion unit (Milestone, Italy) according to the even steps power-controlled digestion program. The cooled digests were quantitatively transferred into 25 volumetric flasks, filled up to the volume with ultrapure water, and mixed properly. The total Au and Fe levels were accessed using an Agilent 7700x ICP-MS (Agilent Technologies Ltd., Japan) using 8-point external calibration and the reliability of ICP-MS results was controlled by a regular measurement of an independently prepared quality control sample. All ICP-MS measurements were performed in six replicates, and the results are expressed as an average \pm standard deviation (SD).

2.3.3. MR relaxometry

The MR relaxometry was utilized to determine the relaxivities r_1 and r_2 of the APEBM nanocomposite. The relaxation times T_1 and T_2 were measured on a relaxometer Bruker Minispec mq60 (Bruker Biospin, Ettlingen, Germany) at 1.5 T and stabilized temperatures of 20 °C and 37 °C during the whole experiment. Before imaging, a concentration series (denoted as 100%, 75%, 50%, and 25%) of the dialyzed APPBM nanocomposite was prepared, and distilled water served as a reference (labelled as H_2O). T_1 relaxation times were measured employing the inversion recovery (IR) sequence: repetition time (TR) = 0.01–10000 ms, recycle delay = 4 s, scans = 4, monoexponential fitting, 10 data points for fitting. T_2 relaxation times were measured using the Carr-Purcell-Meiboom-Gill (CPMG) pulse sequence: echo time (TE) = 0.05 ms, recycle delay = 2 s, scans = 8, monoexponential fitting, 20,000 data points per fitting. The relaxivities r_1 and r_2 were then calculated via the least-squares curve fitting of R_1 and R_2 relaxation rates [s^{-1}] versus real iron concentration [mM], which was determined by ICP-MS. The experimentally determined solvent (distilled water) relaxation rate R_0 was subtracted as a starting value from the nanocomposite relaxation rates prior to the linear regression analysis. Each sample was subjected to three measurements under identical conditions.

2.3.4. *In vitro* MR imaging

In vitro MR imaging was performed on a Bruker Biospec 47/20 (Bruker, Ettlingen, Germany) scanner at 4.7 T. Both T_1 - and T_2 -weighted MR images of the APEBM nanocomposite samples and distilled water (serving as a reference) were acquired using the Rapid Acquisition with Relaxation Enhancement (RARE) sequence. T_1 -weighted sequence: TR = 400 ms, TE = 12 ms, number of acquisitions (NA) = 8, rare factor (RF) = 1, ST = 10 min 14 s, spatial resolution = $0.021 \times 0.021 \text{ mm}^2$, slice thickness = 0.6 mm; T_2 -weighted sequence: TR = 3300 ms, TE = 36 ms, NA = 1 and 5, RF = 1 and 5, ST = 10 min 33 s and 10 min 27 s, spatial resolution = $0.021 \times 0.021 \text{ mm}^2$, slice thickness = 0.6 mm. MR image processing and quantification were performed using ImageJ software developed by the National Institutes of Health (Stapleton, NY, USA). Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was calculated from images as $0.655 \times S_{\text{sample}}/\sigma_{\text{noise}}$ and contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR) was calculated from images as $0.655 \times |S_{\text{sample}} - S_{\text{water}}|/\sigma_{\text{noise}}$, where S is signal intensity in the region of interest, σ is the standard deviation of background noise, and constant 0.655 reflects the Rician distribution of background noise in a magnitude MR image.

2.3.5. *In vitro* optical imaging

The *in vitro* optical imaging was performed using the SPECTRAL Ami HT imager with the subsequent image processing and quantification utilizing the Aura imaging software developed by the Spectral instruments imaging (Tucson, AZ, USA). The experiment involved

phantoms containing four different APEBM nanocomposite concentrations (100%, 75%, 50%, 25%) and distilled water, serving as a reference (labelled as H₂O). The imaging procedure included various excitation and emission ranges to identify the optimal filter settings. Specifically, the excitation at 430/500 nm and emission at 730/670 nm were used, respectively. Other parameters were set as follows: excitation power = 4, exposure time = 2 s, FOV = 15, F-stop = 2, binning = 2.

2.3.6. Fluorescence spectroscopy and dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Fluorescence measurements of the APEBM nanocomposite were performed on a JASCO F8500 (Jasco, Tokyo, Japan) spectrofluorometer using a 1 cm quartz cuvette. Emission spectra were measured in the 505–850 nm range with the data interval of 1 nm and scan speed of 100 nm·min⁻¹. The excitation wavelength was set to 430 nm and 500 nm. All spectra were corrected to avoid any deviations induced by instrumental components.

The hydrodynamic diameter and zeta potential of both systems were determined by dynamic light scattering using Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments Ltd, Malvern, UK) equipped with a He-Ne laser ($\lambda = 633$ nm) at 22 ± 1 °C. For both fluorescence and DLS measurements, the ratio of sample dilution with deionized water was the same (specifically, dialysed samples were diluted 26.66 times).

2.3.7. Calcein-AM assay

In a typical viability assessment, 80 μ L of cultivation medium and cell suspension (RPE-1 cell line) was introduced into a 96-well plate (5000 cells per well), which was afterward put inside the incubator (37 °C, 5% CO₂) for 24 h. Subsequently, 20 μ L of deionized water was pipetted to the second and third column, and eight different concentrations of the APEBM nanocomposite were pipetted in the form of hexaplicates. 24 h later, each well was washed with 95 μ L of PBS two times. Then, 100 μ L of calcein-AM was added into each well. After 1 h of incubation, fluorescence intensity was measured on a microplate fluorometer Fluoroskan Ascent (Finland). The excitation and emission wavelengths were set to 485 nm and 538 nm, respectively. Cell viability (CV) was then calculated according to equation (1):

$$CV = 100 \times \frac{F_{\text{sample}} - F_{\text{medium}}}{F_{\text{cells}} - F_{\text{medium}}}, \quad (1)$$

where F is the averaged fluorescence intensity and subscripts sample, cells, and medium indicate the measurement of fluorescence in the suspensions of sample-treated cells, non-treated cells, and the solution of cultivation medium alone, respectively.

2.3.8. Assessment of fluorescence signal stability in different media under varying temperatures and in the presence of HeLa cells

For the investigation of the fluorescence signal stability in different media, dialyzed APEBM nanocomposite was diluted with PBS and/or cultivation medium. The factor of dilution was kept the same as for the cell viability experiment (i.e., 5 times). For the first 24 h, diluted samples were stored at 4 °C and the emission spectra were measured after 1, 2, and 24 h. Subsequently, diluted samples were kept at room temperature (20 °C) and the emission spectra were measured after 48, 72, and 96 h. Finally, diluted samples were incubated in a dry bath incubator (the temperature was set to 37 °C to simulate the body temperature) and the emission spectra were measured after 168, 192, 216, 240, and 267 h. All spectra were measured on a JASCO F8500 (Jasco, Tokyo, Japan) for the excitation wavelength of 500 nm and were corrected to avoid any deviations induced by instrumental components. Other parameters were set the same as described in chapter 2.3.6. Fluorescence spectroscopy and dynamic light scattering (DLS).

Regarding the fluorescence signal stability in the presence of cells, 80 μ L of cultivation medium and cell suspension (HeLa cell line) was introduced into a 96-well plate (5000 cells per well), which was afterwards put inside the incubator (37 °C, 5% CO₂) for 24 h. Subsequently,

20 μ L of deionized water or dialyzed APEBM nanocomposite were pipetted to the medium and cell suspension in the form of hexaplicates. Then, 1, 2, and 24 h later, fluorescence intensity was measured on a microplate fluorometer Fluoroskan Ascent (Finland). The excitation and emission wavelengths were set to 500 nm and 670 nm, respectively. Fluorescence intensity was further monitored by inverted fluorescent microscope (Olympus Microscope IX51 with Fluorescence and Phase Contrasts, Japan) in the cultivation medium in the presence vs. absence of HeLa cells as a function of time.

2.3.9. In vivo experiments – optical imaging and MRI

A healthy female BALB/c mouse was housed in a temperature-controlled room with a 12-hour light–dark cycle and free access to food pellets and water. The animal preparation procedure was carried out under complete anaesthesia using isoflurane (5% for induction and 1.5–2% for maintenance), which was purchased from Baxter (Deerfield, IL, USA). To avoid eye dryness and its potential damage, an eye cream Ophthmo-Septonex purchased from Zentiva (Prague, Czech Republic) was thoroughly applied. Additionally, all four limbs were carefully shaved to minimize the optical signal attenuation, leaving a sufficient area around the injection site.

Before *in vivo* optical imaging, the right upper limb and both lower limbs were subcutaneously injected, each with a different replicate of the dialyzed APEBM nanocomposite. Every injection contained 100 μ L of the replicate, which was previously diluted 1.33 times (denoted as 75% concentration). The left upper limb was injected with distilled water serving as a reference. Immediately after the injections, optical images were acquired using the identical spectral parameters as those applied during the *in vitro* experiments.

Right before the *in vivo* MR imaging, all four limbs were additionally injected with 100 μ L of the corresponding APEBM nanocomposite with the intention of enhancing the visualization and signal quality due to potential animal movement and the elapsed time between optical and MR imaging, which could result in a partial absorption of the contrast agent. For the *in vivo* MRI experiment, the homemade birdcage coil was used. Furthermore, the respiratory rate of the mouse was monitored throughout the whole experiment using a trigger unit purchased from Rapid Biomedical (Berlin, Germany). We acquired both T₁- and T₂-weighted MR images using the Rapid Acquisition with Relaxation Enhancement (RARE) sequence, employing the *in vitro* imaging protocol. To speed up the scan time, we just modified these parameters: NA = 4, RF = 8, ST = 5 min 16 s, and spatial resolution = 0.03×0.03 mm². Then, MRI data were processed and analysed using ImageJ.

All animal protocols were approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine and the Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic (no. 58/2014) in accordance with the European Communities Council Directive (2010/63/EU).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Optimized green synthesis of the APEBM nanocomposite and visualization via HR-TEM

In our previous work [15], we successfully developed a facile one-pot green synthesis of functional magneto-luminescent bimetallic nanocomposites, combining luminescent AuNC together with SPION via BSA. However, to achieve a sufficient MRI contrast, these nanocomposites had to be concentrated [15]. Simultaneously, the viscosity of the nanocomposite solutions increased. Since the increased viscosity would be a problem in any *in vivo* application, we decided to further modify and substantially optimize our synthetic approach (details are carefully discussed in Supporting Information and clearly presented in Table SI-1) and, thus, the APEBM nanocomposite was developed. Indeed, numerous preparation trials (including multiple combinations of molar ratios between protein and both metals, different order and timings of reactants addition, various pH changes amongst certain steps of the synthesis, and

several temperatures during the sample maturing in a dry bath incubator) were attempted to increase metals concentration in the final bimetallic nanocomposites with the aim of contrast signals improvement. The stability of the bimetallic nanocomposite was quite challenging because the aggregation either of iron oxide nanoparticles, or of the protein itself often occurred (Table SI-1). Finally, we succeeded in overcoming any aggregation and the specifically optimized synthetic approach respecting green chemistry principles (i.e., usage of aqueous environment, non-toxic species, and omission of abundant chemicals) was developed, i.e., the APEBM nanocomposite created. The optimized synthesis of the APEBM nanocomposite is schematically depicted in Fig. 1.

By direct comparison of the schematic depiction of the APEBM nanocomposite synthesis presented here (Fig. 1) with that used in our previous work [15], one can clearly see the substantial changes in the synthetic approach. There are several, as specified step by step below: (i) type of iron precursor/s employed; (ii) order of reactants addition; (iii) fine pH adjustment prior to auric acid addition (the newly introduced step); (iv) prolonged time among individual steps of the synthesis; (v) type of heating for the acceleration of both chemical processes, Au (III) reduction and SPION formation, under alkaline pH; (vi) increased reaction time and elevated temperature of sample maturation. Importantly, the final APEBM nanocomposite is very stable against aggregation even at elevated metal concentrations; the theoretical molar ratios of BSA: Au: Fe are 1: 20: 20 in the present work, as compared to the ratios of 1: 10: 0.75 reported in our previous article [15]. This could be achieved most probably by the newly involved step among others, i.e., increasing the pH to slightly alkaline (pH = 7.4) before adding a gold precursor. Around this pH value, ferric ions predominantly form neutral aqua complexes [32]. The neutrality may probably lead to a better interaction between the iron complex and the protein molecule (being in its close to natural conformation at the adjusted slightly alkaline pH value). Moreover, it should be pinpointed that a video of the whole synthesis was recorded, showing how BSA and other reactants are slowly pipetted into a tube and mixed together – see Supporting Information.

The final optimized APEBM nanocomposite is visualized using HR-TEM (bright field) and STEM (dark field) as shown in Fig. 2A and Fig. 2B, respectively. It is evident that objects of sizes around 1.6 nm are frequently encountered by both imaging modes. Elemental composition is verified via energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy and the characteristic spectrum is shown in Fig. 2C. It clearly evidenced the simultaneous presence of gold (coming from luminescent AuNC), iron (stemming from SPION), and sulphur (representative element evidencing the protein presence directly since any other reactants within the reaction mixture do not contain S). The signal of the other elements detected in the EDS spectrum comes either from the microscopic grid (e.g., Cu, C) and/or from the species being present in the reaction mixture (e.g., O, C, N, Na). Randomly chosen place of APEBM nanocomposite deposited on TEM holey carbon-covered Cu-grid was mapped (area framed by green square in Fig. 2D) as for selected elements (Au, Fe, S) distribution (Fig. 2E).

Fig. 1. Schematic depiction of the APEBM nanocomposite synthesis.

Obviously, protein (detected via S) is spread in the selected area almost homogeneously (blue spots in Fig. 2E). On the other hand, AuNC (green spots) and SPION (red spots) are either co-localized and/or arranged into specific agglomerates as can be clearly seen in Fig. 2E. Regarding the brightness of spots in Fig. 2D (dark field mode), it well corresponds to the elemental composition determined by EDS mapping in Fig. 2E: the brighter and well-separated nanoobjects are AuNC; while somewhat less bright, tiny nanostructures agglomerated into chains can be attributed to SPION. It should be, however, reminded that samples for HR-TEM/STEM/EDS mapping are drop-casted on the microscopic grid and allowed to dry which means that the effect of drying can influence the observed structural arrangement of APEBM nanocomposite. Moreover, it was corroborated in our recent work [33] that the focused electron beam during HR-TEM and EDS mapping can greatly modify the oxidation states of metallic parts as well as their mobility within our nanocomposites, leading thus to structural rearrangement *in situ*, under the electron beam. Consequently, a modified sample is measured and not the as-synthesized one.

3.2. *In vitro* MR imaging and relaxometry using the APEBM nanocomposite

SPION are considered as efficient T₂ MRI contrast agents since they can influence the transverse (or spin-spin) relaxation time of protons [34]. The T₂-weighted MR images representing the observed MR signal from four different concentrations of the dialyzed APEBM nanocomposite samples (denoted as 100%, 75%, 50%, and 25%) are shown in Table 1, along with distilled water (serving as reference).

By their direct comparison, it is evident that the contrast is sufficiently visible even in the case of the lowest concentration (25%) of the APEBM nanocomposite. Thus, the APEBM nanocomposite is affecting the relaxation time of surrounding water protons. This observation can also be supported numerically with the quantitative imaging parameters: signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR), which are summarized in the table included as an inset in Table 1. Specifically, the higher the concentration of the sample (iron concentration), the shorter the relaxation time of water protons and, consequently, the higher the change of contrast in MR images was found. These changes reflect the increasing differences in the SNR and CNR values between the APEBM nanocomposite samples and the reference (distilled water). Additionally, T₁-weighted imaging was carried out as well; however, the MR signal from the APEBM nanocomposite was only slightly different than the signal from the reference (Table SI-2), which is in accordance with the majority of scientific literature (e.g., [15,18]). It can be noted that only under favourable preparation conditions, it is feasible to obtain SPION with a relatively high T₁ contrast and low r₂/r₁ ratio [35,36].

Besides the MR imaging in phantoms, relaxometry measurements were conducted to obtain the relaxivity values. Experimentally determined relaxation times T₁ and T₂ were used to calculate the relaxation rates R₁ and R₂ as reciprocal values, respectively. Then, the dependence of the relaxation rate on the real iron concentration was plotted. The real iron concentration in the dialyzed APEBM nanocomposite samples was determined by ICP-MS and is listed in Table SI-3. Subsequently, the experimental R₁ and R₂ values were fitted with a linear function according to equation (1), as shown in Figures SI-1A, SI-1B, and SI-1C. The slope of this function represents the corresponding relaxivity r. Both r₁ and r₂ values are listed in Table SI-4, together with the r₂/r₁ ratio. Indeed, the r₂/r₁ ratio is an important factor correlating with the imaging contrast efficiency. For T₂-weighted contrast agents, it is commonly higher than 2 [37]. According to the results, the r₂/r₁ ratio of the APEBM nanocomposite is slightly higher than 10 (Table SI-4), which is fully comparable with the r₂/r₁ ratios of the commercially available iron oxide nanoparticle-based contrast agents, such as ferucarbotran (Resovist®), ferumoxides (Feridex®), and ferumoxtran-10 (Combinex®), measured in water at 1.5 T [38–40]. It is important to stress that our relaxometry measurement was conducted at 1.5 T, a magnetic field

Fig. 2. (A) HR-TEM (bright field) and (B) STEM (dark field) images of APEBM nanocomposite. (C) Its EDS spectrum. (D) Randomly chosen place of deposited APEBM nanocomposite to map the elemental composition within a framed area (green square). (E) Selected elements distribution within the map shown in (D). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

strength commonly employed in clinical practice. Furthermore, it should be remembered that the relaxivity and the r_2/r_1 ratio could depend on many parameters, including the field strength, used medium (water, plasma, or blood), and protein corona [37,38]. To sum up, the experimentally determined r_2/r_1 ratio of the APEBM nanocomposite

renders it the capability of a potential MR contrast agent with a beneficial luminescent property (as will be evidenced in the next section).

Table 1

T₂-weighted MR images of phantoms representing four different concentrations (labelled as 100%, 75%, 50%, and 25%) of a representative APEBM nanocomposite sample and distilled water serving as a reference (labelled as H₂O), with corresponding signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) and contrast-to-noise-ratio (CNR) values.

Sample concentration	100%	75%	50%	25%	H ₂ O
T ₂ -weighted MR signal					
SNR	8.34	11.22	13.37	13.70	17.59
CNR	9.24	6.36	4.22	3.89	

3.3. *In vitro* optical imaging employing the APEBM nanocomposite

Embedded in BSA, AuNC can exhibit bright luminescence in the visible and near-infrared regions with relatively high quantum yield [41–44]. Therefore, we tested optical imaging using our optimized APEBM nanocomposites *in vitro*. The images depicting the observed luminescence signal from four different concentrations of the dialyzed APEBM nanocomposite samples (the same concentration series as used in the MRI and relaxometry measurements) are shown in Fig. 3, together with distilled water (serving as reference).

The luminescence signal for each concentration of the APEBM nanocomposite is strong, i.e., even for the lowest concentration (25%), the emission signal is more than 40 times stronger than the reference signal (excitation and emission wavelengths were 500 nm and 670 nm, respectively). A similar pattern can be observed in Figure SI-2, where a different set of excitation and emission wavelengths (excitation and emission wavelengths were 430 nm and 730 nm, respectively) was used. However, the latter set of wavelengths is out of the optimal range, thus the emission intensities presented in Figure SI-2 are lower than those shown in Fig. 3. Moreover, the results for both excitation/emission sets correspond with the fluorescence measurements of the APEBM nanocomposite in a diluted state (thus avoiding the inner filter effect), as can be seen in Figure SI-3.

In all four concentrations of the APEBM nanocomposite (Fig. 3 and Figure SI-2), the inner filter effect is reflected to a certain extent in the resulting emission intensity: the higher the concentration, the more pronounced the effect is. Alternatively, the dependence of the emission intensity on the sample concentration within this concentration range is non-linear. Consequently, the emission intensity for the 75% concentration of the APEBM nanocomposite sample is higher than that for the 100% concentration within both wavelength sets (Table SI-5 and SI-6). It can be summarized that the APEBM nanocomposite is an efficient fluorescent imaging probe when using appropriate concentration and

excitation/emission wavelengths and, thus, could be applied for *in vivo* experiments.

3.4. Biocompatibility and other important characteristics of the APEBM nanocomposite

Prior to performing the *in vivo* imaging experiments, some other characteristics of the APEBM nanocomposite, which can influence its interaction within a living organism, were determined. Specifically, *in vitro* cell viability, particle size distribution, zeta potential of the APEBM nanocomposite and fluorescence signal stability in different media (e.g., PBS, cultivation medium) under varying temperatures and with/without cells presence were measured and assessed.

As for the cell viability assessment, a fluorometric calcein-AM assay was established. Widely used colorimetric MTT, XTT assays, and a fluorometric Alamar blue (resazurin) assay were not employed because of the possible interaction between the protein matrix (BSA) and the corresponding dye, which could lead to false positive or negative results, as discussed in [45–47]. Cell viability was determined for eight different concentrations of the APEBM nanocomposite, as shown in Table SI-7. Even for the highest concentration (labelled as 99%), the viability is higher than 90% (specifically, $93.5 \pm 1.1\%$). The closest value to the one used for both *in vitro* and *in vivo* imaging is the concentration of 70%, with its corresponding viability of $103.5 \pm 0.5\%$. These values fulfil the condition for APEBM nanocomposite to be considered a non-toxic species according to ISO 10993.

Dynamic light scattering was employed for particle size distribution and zeta potential determination of the APEBM nanocomposite in aqueous solution to provide relevant information about the particle size distribution of the entire APEBM nanocomposite in solution, i.e., the hydrodynamic diameter (usually much bigger than sizes determined by TEM measurements for the same sample). DLS has been recommended in a very recent review [44] to tackle this and, therefore, used by us. The

Fig. 3. *In vitro* fluorescence image of phantoms representing four different concentrations (labelled as 100%, 75%, 50%, and 25%) of a representative APEBM nanocomposite sample and distilled water serving as a reference (labelled as H₂O). Excitation and emission wavelengths were 500 nm and 670 nm, respectively.

average values of the polydispersity index (PDI), Z-average, hydrodynamic diameter (based on the changes of scattered light intensity), and zeta potential are listed in Table 2, together with their standard deviations. The measured particle size distribution derived from the changes in scattered light intensity is shown in Figure SI-4.

Obviously, the APEBM nanocomposite possesses a somewhat broad monomodal size distribution and negative zeta potential value. The higher negative value of zeta potential indicates that the APEBM nanocomposite should be stable. However, their stability and particularly the stability of fluorescence signal have to be further checked within the cell cultivation medium used. Thus, we evaluated the integrated fluorescence intensity of APEBM samples within selected media (PBS and/or cultivation medium) under varying temperatures and related it to the averaged integrated fluorescence intensity of APEBM samples in deionized water. The results (graphically depicted in Figure SI-5A) show that integrated fluorescence intensities of APEBM sample in PBS and/or cultivation medium are well above that of APEBM sample in deionized water. The position of emission maximum (Figure SI-5B) slightly shifts in the cultivation medium under varying temperatures in the course of time. Fluorescence intensity was further monitored by inverted fluorescent microscope in the cultivation medium in the presence vs. absence of HeLa cells as a function of time. HeLa cancer cells were intentionally chosen for this type of experiment as inspired by [28]. It corroborated the stability of fluorescence signal after 1, 2, and 24 h of cells incubation (Figure SI-6).

Although both the hydrodynamic diameter and surface charge (which is generally represented as zeta potential), play a certain role within the nanomaterial-cell interactions [48–54], many other factors can also affect the cellular internalization and/or the cytotoxicity of the investigated nanomaterial, including, for instance, the shape [55,56], composition of metal core/surface [56,57], elasticity [58,59], hydrophobicity [57,60], and last but not least, protein corona presence and composition [56,61–63]. The last issue can be modulated by the physicochemical properties of the nanomaterial, surrounding biological environment (e.g., pH, ionic strength, temperature, and plasma concentration) or even the cholesterol levels as known from the literature [61,64–67]. Evidently, the cell internalization of the nanomaterial inside a biological system is very complex since it depends on numerous interconnected parameters. Therefore, besides the *in vitro* imaging, *in vivo* imaging should be performed to verify both the MR and optical contrasts inside a living organism (animal).

3.5. *In vivo* imaging exploiting the APEBM nanocomposite

Since both *in vitro* MR and optical imaging techniques provided significant change of contrasts from the reference (distilled water), *in vitro* viability experiments proved the biocompatibility of the APEBM nanocomposite even for the highest concentration, *in vivo* imaging experiments were performed. Three replicates of the dialyzed APEBM nanocomposite sample were subcutaneously injected, each into a different limb of a healthy female BALB/c mouse. Based on the results of *in vitro* experiments and considering the potential inner filter effect, the three *in vivo* injections contained a 75% concentration of the APEBM nanocomposite sample. In the fourth limb of the healthy mouse, distilled water (reference) was injected. Immediately after the injections, both optical and MR imaging were conducted, and the images representing

Table 2

Average values of hydrodynamic diameter (based on the changes of scattered light intensity), Z-Average, PDI and zeta potential acquired by DLS measurements of a representative APEBM nanocomposite sample, listed with their standard deviations.

Hydrodynamic diameter [nm]	Z-Average [nm]	PDI	Zeta potential [mV]
296 ± 14	220 ± 3	0.295 ± 0.011	−44 ± 2

the observed luminescence and MR signals are shown in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively.

Evidently, each of the three injection sites, where the APEBM nanocomposite was introduced, exhibits both luminescence and MR signals; while the reference (in the fourth limb) did not provide a detectable impact on the signal given by the local tissue. The luminescence signal from the APEBM nanocomposite is at least 20 times stronger than the signal from the reference (Fig. 4). Similarly, the MR contrast induced by the APEBM nanocomposite can be easily distinguished from the surrounding muscle tissue (Fig. 5A and Fig. 5B).

There are some differences among the intensities of individual replicates, but they may stem from anatomical dissimilarities under the skin within the injection site, subsequently leading to variabilities in the distribution of the APEBM nanocomposite. Furthermore, absorption and scattering of the excitation (namely) and emission wavelengths when they pass through the different thicknesses of skin tissue during optical imaging could alter the resulting intensities. Moreover, the varying position of each limb with respect to the emitter and detector during the imaging procedures could also have an impact on the signal.

Additionally, it has to be stated that MR imaging was performed at 4.7 T. This magnetic field strength closely approaches the clinically used one (3 T). Consequently, the results of MR imaging exploiting the APEBM nanocomposite are tremendously important for clinical research and, hence, the potential translation of the APEBM nanocomposite into

Fig. 4. *In vivo* fluorescence image of a healthy female BALB/c mouse under anaesthesia. Three replicates (denoted as BM1, BM2, and BM3) of the APEBM nanocomposite were subcutaneously injected, each into a different limb. Each injection contained a 75% concentration of the replicate, whereas distilled water was injected into the upper left limb serving as a reference. Excitation and emission wavelengths were 500 nm and 670 nm, respectively.

Fig. 5. (A, B) *In vivo* MR images of a healthy female BALB/c mouse under anaesthesia. Three replicates (denoted as BM1, BM2, and BM3) of the APEBM nanocomposite were subcutaneously injected, each into a different limb. Each injection contained 75% concentration of the replicate, whereas distilled water was injected into the upper left limb serving as a reference.

clinical practice can be envisaged.

Importantly, three months after the imaging experiments, the weight of the animal increased (by 10 % in the first month). The treated areas on the animal's body were also inspected visually and did not show any signs of inflammation, or other pathologies. This supports the conclusion from cytotoxicity testing that the APEBM nanocomposite has no harmful effects and can be considered biocompatible.

To sum up, the APEBM nanocomposite can be successfully exploited as a bimodal FI/MRI contrast agent in a living organism. To the best of our knowledge, the APEBM nanocomposite is the very first bimodal FI/MRI biocompatible probe based solely on nanostructured entities entrapped within a protein matrix and successfully applied *in vivo*. While the existence of T₂-weighted magnetic contrast is caused by the presence of SPION, similarly as in [34], the luminescence is exhibited by AuNC, as in e.g. [68]. Therefore, both signals are provided by two different inorganic nanostructured entities that are embedded in the same transportation protein. It can be remembered here that using a bimodal contrast probe can overcome the limitations of the monomodal probes [69]. In the case of MRI/FI, where the MR and fluorescence signals could be detected simultaneously, the advantage lies in the combination of high spatial resolution and penetration depth of MRI, and high fluorescence sensitivity [69]. Moreover, SPION are widely recognized as inert imaging agents devoid of intended pharmacological functions [70]. These nanoparticles are commonly classified as biocompatible, demonstrating negligible *in vivo* toxicity [71,72]. Our investigations of newly developed APEBM nanocomposites reveal similar inert characteristics. Due to their non-specificity and lack of functional surface modifications, we propose that APEBM nanocomposites could potentially serve as efficient liver contrast agents for future applications. In this respect, we were inspired also by the results of Zhang and co-workers [73] who observed high Au content for the BSA-protected Au₂₅ NCs in liver and suggested to use it in targeting therapy for liver cancer. It could be a direction for ongoing research, however, it is beyond the scope of this work. Last but not least, obtaining a biocompatible dual contrast agent utilizing SPION in conjunction with a fluorescent probe is relatively difficult because of the possible aggregation of iron oxide nanoparticles and their strong absorption [74], which could cause the luminescence quenching to a certain extent. In the case of the APEBM nanocomposite, the absorption of SPION together with the emission of AuNC are ideally shifted (Figure SI-7): SPION absorb mainly in the UV region and, in a decreasing manner, in the visible region [74]; whereas the AuNC emit more towards the NIR region (Figure SI-7). It should also be pinpointed that *in vivo* fluorescence visualization is quite challenging [75]. The APEBM nanocomposite is highly stable (based on the zeta potential value listed in Table 2, spectroscopic monitoring over

a year of shelf-life when stored in a fridge, and assessment of fluorescence signal stability in different media under varying temperatures and in the presence of HeLa cells), which can be related to the specifically optimized green synthetic approach developed and adopted in the present work. It can be even envisaged that other metal cations suitable for achieving additional functionality of a resulting nanocomposite (e.g., theranostic purposes and/or multimodal imaging), will be easily incorporated due to the robustness of the developed synthesis. Ongoing research is conducted by us in this direction.

4. Conclusions

Highly optimized one-pot sequential green synthesis of the APEBM nanocomposite resulted in a very stable, reproducible product that was proved capable of serving as an efficient FI/MRI biocompatible bimodal contrast agent *in vitro* as well as *in vivo*. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first bimodal imaging probe of its kind in the world since it combines totally nontoxic components (AuNC, SPION, serum albumin), hence ensuring biocompatibility of the entire nanocomposite; and effectively exploits functionalities of each part, avoiding thus any redundancy. It can be noticed here that the usage of a bimodal contrast probe can overcome the limitations of the monomodal ones [69]. It should also be pinpointed that *in vivo* fluorescence visualization is quite challenging [75]. Since the APEBM nanocomposite is based solely on nanostructured entities entrapped within a protein matrix, it renders the system flexible which can be further developed and exploited.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Radek Ostruszka: Formal analysis, Investigation (DLS, fluorescence), Methodology (optimized synthesis of the APEBM nanocomposite), Original draft writing. **Aminadav Halili:** Formal analysis, Investigation (FI and MRI in phantoms and *in vivo*). **Tomáš Pluháček:** Formal analysis, Investigation (ICP-MS analyses), Original draft editing. **Lucie Rárová:** Formal analysis, Investigation (biocompatibility), Methodology. **Daniel Jiráček:** Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation (FI and MRI *in vivo*), Methodology, Original draft editing. **Karolína Šisková:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing and editing original draft, original draft - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2024.02.116>.

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